

3D PRINTING OF STIFF PHOTONIC MICROPARTICLES INTO LOAD-BEARING STRUCTURES

*Pauline Pradal, Paul Hardivillé, Jong Bin Kim, Seong Kyeong Nam, Shin-Hyun Kim, Esther Amstad**

Pauline Pradal, Paul Hardivillé, Esther Amstad
Soft Materials Laboratory - Institute of Materials in École Polytechnique Fédérale de Lausanne,
1015 Lausanne, Switzerland
E-mail: esther.amstad@epfl.ch

Jong Bin Kim
Department of Materials Science and Engineering, University of Pennsylvania, 19104
Philadelphia, USA

Seong Kyeong Nam, Shin-Hyun Kim
Department of Chemical and Biomolecular Engineering - Korea Advanced Institute of Science
and Technology (KAIST), 34141 Daejeon, Republic of Korea

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Structural colors are bright and possess a remarkable resistance to light exposure, humidity and temperature such that they constitute an environmentally friendly alternative to chemical pigments. Unfortunately, upscaling the production of photonic structures obtained via conventional colloidal self-assembly is challenging because defects often occur during the assembly of larger structures. Moreover, the processing of materials exhibiting structural colors into intricate 3D structures remains challenging. To address these limitations, we formulate rigid photonic microparticles into an ink that can be 3D printed through direct ink writing (DIW) at room temperature to form intricate macroscopic structures possessing locally varying mechanical and optical properties. This is achieved by adding small amounts of soft microgels to the rigid photonic particles. To rigidify the granular structure, we form a percolating hydrogel network that covalently connects the microgels. The mechanical properties of the resulting photonic granular materials can be adjusted with the composition and volume fraction of the microgels. We demonstrate the potential of this approach by 3D printing a centimeter-sized photonic butterfly and a temperature-responsive photonic material.

1. Introduction

Structural colors manifest in various organisms such as birds, fishes, insects like the Morpho butterfly, jewel beetle and kingfisher and are generally used for camouflage, communication and thermoregulation.^[1-4] Structural colors arise from the interaction of light with periodic nanostructures made of two dielectric materials, creating vivid colors through constructive interferences. Motivated by the brightness and vividness of natural materials exhibiting

structural colors, similar colors have been synthetically produced for instance by exploiting multilayer interferences, diffraction gratings and photonic crystals.^[5] These structural colors have been used, for example, as photonic sensors^[2], anti-counterfeiting features^[6] and in displays^[7].

Colloidal self-assembly can be employed to produce vivid structural colors, for example by embedding silica nanoparticles (SiO₂ NPs) within acrylate-based resins.^[8–10] The resulting color typically depends on the size and volume fraction of the SiO₂ NPs, which determine their average interparticle distance and, consequently, the periodicity of the nanostructure.^[11,12] To enhance the purity of the reflected light, these NPs are embedded in a transparent polymer like poly(ethylene glycol phenyl ether acrylate) (pEGPEA) or poly(ethoxylated trimethylolpropane triacrylate) (pETPTA), which minimizes unwanted scattering and absorbance.^[13] When dispersed in hydrophobic acrylate-based precursor solutions, a solvation layer forms on the NP surfaces, causing them to self-assemble into non-close-packed face-centered cubic-like (FCC) structures.^[12,13] Upon solidification of the precursor achieved through a free radical polymerization of the acrylates, stiff structures form. Various methods including micromolding^[11], DIW^[14], microfluidics^[9,15,16] and photolithography^[8,10,13,17], have been explored to shape these photonic crystals into 2D films^[8,11,13,14], microspheres^[9,15,16], and microcylinders^[10,17]. However, most of the photonic structures are processed into simple structures, with at least one dimension limited to a few hundred micrometers. To enable their processing into 3D structures, SiO₂ NPs have been self-assembled within drops to microcompartmentalize them, enabling the formulation of printable structural color inks.^[9,18,19] The ETPTA-based drops containing SiO₂ NPs have been transformed into photonic microparticles by polymerizing the reagents contained in them. However, the maximum volume fraction of SiO₂ NPs that can be achieved within dispersions is limited by the strong increase in the viscosity of the precursor solution that prevents its controlled processing into drops through microfluidics.^[20] Moreover, these microparticles are too rigid to yield, preventing their extrusion through DIW.^[21,22] This limitation can be overcome through the addition of soft microparticles.^[23] Indeed, microparticles with different stiffnesses have been co-printed as mixed inks or by sequentially depositing them layer-by-layer to locally vary the stiffness of granular substrates.^[24,25] However, this approach was limited to printing particles with stiffnesses not exceeding a few hundreds of kPa.^[26] Co-printing microparticles with larger differences in stiffnesses and compositions risks causing agglomeration between particles. These agglomerates tend to clog the printing nozzle and lead to uncontrolled heterogeneities in the composition and stiffness of the resulting material. Strategies that mitigate these risks and enable a reliable co-printing of microparticles with large stiffness variations, spanning several MPa, remain to be demonstrated.

We introduce a photonic ink that can be 3D printed at room temperature through DIW and processed into mechanically stable photonic structures with Young's moduli varying between 50 and 300 kPa. This is achieved by mixing rigid pETPTA-based photonic microparticles with soft hydrogel microparticles, so-called microgels. We demonstrate that the rheological properties of mixtures of densely packed pETPTA microparticles encompassing as little as 2 wt% microgels are ideal for DIW. The 3D printed granular structure is rigidified by forming a

percolating hydrogel network that interpenetrates the microgels and covalently connects them. Thereby, we obtain mechanically stable cm-sized materials. We use design of experiments (DOE) to optimize the printing fidelity by adjusting the ink composition. The potential of this ink is demonstrated by 3D printing a cm-sized caterpillar with locally varying mechanical or optical properties. These results highlight the versatility and potential of these inks for 3D printing of intricate cm-sized structures with tailored mechanical and optical properties.

2. Results and discussion

2.1. Preparation of granular inks containing rigid building blocks

Microgels are well suited for DIW if concentrated to a particle-to-volume fraction above 0.58, thanks to their shear-thinning and self-healing behavior.^[27–29] To obtain the rheological properties required for DIW, microgels must jam. Microparticles composed of pETPTA are stiff since pETPTA displays a Young's modulus of order tens of MPa^[21], such that pETPTA microparticles cannot be jammed. To modify their rheological properties and enable DIW-based 3D printing of pETPTA microparticles, we mix them with soft poly(2-acrylamido-2-methyl-1-propanesulfonic acid) (pAMPS) microgels. PETPTA microparticles are prepared from oil-in-water (O/W) drops. To control the size of these drops, they are produced in a parallelized polydimethylsiloxane (PDMS)-based microfluidic device, the millipede device, as depicted in **Figure 1a**.^[20] The oil phase is composed of ETPTA containing 1 wt% photoinitiator (PI) whereas the aqueous phase is based on deionized water encompassing 1 wt% of pluronic that we use as a surfactant. The resulting ETPTA drops are polymerized by exposing them to UV light to transform them into pETPTA microparticles.

PAMPS microgels are produced from water-in-oil (W/O) emulsion templates. We employ mineral oil containing 2 wt% of the surfactant span 80 as a continuous phase and an aqueous solution containing AMPS, MBAA and 1 $\mu\text{L}/\text{mL}$ PI as a dispersed phase. The two fluids are mixed at a volume ratio of 3:1 before they are vortexed, as schematically shown in **Figure 1a**.^[30] Drops are converted into microgels by exposing them to UV light for 5 min to initiate the free radical polymerization. The resulting microgels are washed and freeze-dried.

To convert individual microparticles into a 3D printable ink, we mix the dried pETPTA microparticles with pAMPS microgels at a known weight ratio typically ranging between 20:1 and 60:1, as illustrated in **Figure 1b**. The granular ink is centrifuged before being extruded with a commercial 3D bioprinter at pressures not exceeding 100 kPa, as presented in **Figure 1c**. Note that during the centrifugation, we form two distinct layers: the bottom layer is composed of densely packed pETPTA microparticles and the top layer of jammed pAMPS microgels. We assign this separation of the two particle types to their differences in sizes and stiffnesses. To obtain homogeneous inks, we remove the top layer composed of liquid with a pipette before we mechanically mix the two layers of densely packed particles with a spatula. To increase the degree of jamming of the microparticles, we remove additional liquid with a filter paper. To demonstrate the potential of our granular mixed inks, we 3D print a complex, centimeter-sized rock hand from an ink composed of 98 wt% pETPTA microparticles and 2 wt% pAMPS

microgels, as shown in **Figure 1d**. The 77-layer structure is printed at a speed ranging between 2 and 5 mm/s, resulting in a total printing time of approximately 1 h.

Figure 1: Schematic illustration of the 3D printing process of stiff pETPTA microparticles. (a) Monodisperse pETPTA microparticles are produced from oil-in-water drops made with a parallelized microfluidic millipede device. Polydisperse pAMPS particles are produced from water-in-oil drops made through vortexing. (b) The two types of microparticles are mixed and jammed. (c) The resulting ink is printed at room temperature with a bioprinter. (d) Photographs (right) and CAD models (left) of a 3D printed rock-hand made from 77 layers of an ink composed of a mixture of 98 wt% rigid pETPTA microparticles and 2 wt% soft pAMPS microgels. Scale bars: 5 mm.

2.2. Optimization of the printing fidelity

Inks formulated with pETPTA microparticles are shear-thinning, as shown in **Figure S1**. However, due to the high stiffness of the pETPTA microparticles^[31], the flow point is as high as (600 ± 50) kPa, as shown in **Figure S1a**. This stress is too high for the ink to be processed with commercial bioprinters.

We expect pAMPS microgels to impart the rheological properties required for DIW to the pETPTA-based paste. To assess the influence of the size ratio between the pAMPS microgels and the pETPTA microparticles on the rheological properties of pETPTA-based pastes, we produce large pAMPS microgels with a diameter of (117 ± 7) μm and small pETPTA microparticles with a diameter of (70 ± 2) μm using microfluidics, as shown in **Figure S2a-b**. If the diameter of pAMPS microgels exceeds that of pETPTA particles, the latter tend to agglomerate into structures that can clog the printing nozzle, thus preventing a reliable extrusion, as shown in **Figure 2a**. The agglomerations also negatively affect the optical properties: Materials produced from this paste contain transparent regions mainly comprised of pAMPS microgels and white regions mainly comprised of pETPTA particle agglomerates, as shown in **Figure 2a**. To verify that this agglomeration is a result of the larger size of pAMPS microgels

compared to that of pETPTA microparticles, we produce pAMPS microgels and pETPTA particles with similar diameters using batch emulsification. This process yields microgels with diameters between 5 and 40 μm and microparticles with diameters between 10 and 70 μm , as shown in **Figure S2c-d**. Inks comprised of pAMPS microgels with diameters similar to those of rigid pETPTA counterparts can readily be printed through nozzles whose diameter is at least three times larger than the diameter of the rigid particles, as shown in **Figure 2b**.^[32] The presence of a large weight fraction of rigid pETPTA microparticles results in a spreading factor as low as $(20\pm 7)\%$, which is lower than those typically reported for granular microgel-based inks.^[33,34]

A reduction in the diameter of pETPTA particles leads to a decreased brightness of the structural colors due to a lower surface crystallinity of the SiO_2 NPs.^[5] To enhance the vividness and brightness of structural colors of the printed structure without compromising its processibility, we formulate inks composed of monodisperse pETPTA microparticles with a diameter of $(130\pm 3)\ \mu\text{m}$, as shown in **Figure S2b,e**. These particles are much larger than the pAMPS microgels whose diameter ranges from 5 to 40 μm , as shown in **Figure S2d**. We expect the small soft pAMPS microgels to surround the rigid pETPTA particles, thereby acting as a lubricant. Indeed, this ink can be readily 3D printed through a nozzle with a diameter of 410 μm using a commercial bioprinter at pressures as low as (30 ± 5) kPa, as shown in **Figure 2c**. We obtain similar results if we use pETPTA microparticles with a diameter of $(70\pm 2)\ \mu\text{m}$. This result is remarkable because the ink only contains 2 wt% pAMPS microgels and suggests that rigid pETPTA do not form large agglomerates but are surrounded by small pAMPS microgels. This ink exhibits an excellent printing fidelity with a spreading factor as low as $(15\pm 6)\%$, as shown in **Figure 2c**. We assign this result to the presence of a high weight fraction of the rigid pETPTA microparticles. Because of the favorable rheological properties and low spreading factor, we employ inks composed of pETPTA microparticles which are larger than pAMPS microgels for the remainder of this study, unless specified differently.

Figure 2: Schematic illustration of the printing of inks composed of stiff pETPTA microparticles and soft pAMPS microgels as a function of the particle diameters. If the diameter of pETPTA particles is (a) below that of pAMPS microgels, pETPTA microparticles tend to agglomerate, risking to clog the printing nozzle. Mixed inks composed of pETPTA particles whose diameter is (b) similar or (c) at least twice as large as that of the pAMPS microgels are shear-thinning and display self-healing properties. Photographs (top left, scale bar: 2 mm) and optical microscopy images (bottom left, scale bar: 500 μm) of printed square grids used to quantify the spreading factor of mixed inks. The spreading factors are (b) $(20 \pm 7) \%$ and (c) $(15 \pm 6) \%$.

The printing fidelity of granular inks depends on the size and composition of the microgels.^[27,30,35] To optimize the spreading factor, which is an indication for the printing fidelity, we vary the stiffness of the pAMPS microgels by altering the AMPS (c_{AMPS}) and MBAA (c_{MBAA}) concentrations within the drops they are made from. Similarly, we vary the weight fraction of the pAMPS microgels ($\text{wt}\%_{\text{pAMPS}}$) in the final ink and the diameter of the pETPTA particles (Ø_{pETPTA}). To reduce the number of experiments required to optimize the spreading factor, we use design of experiments (DOE), as explained in the Materials and Methods section.

We perform 27 experiments to calculate an empirical model that relates the spreading factor to the 4 processing parameters, as detailed in **Table S1**. From these results, we calculate the spreading factor as the inner area of the printed square grid minus the expected one quantified on optical micrographs acquired from printed grids, normalized by the expected area, as

exemplified in **Figure S3a**.^[33,34] As expected, the spreading factor decreases with increasing printing pressure, as shown in **Figure S3b**. An ANOVA analysis is performed to verify the statistical validity of the coefficients of our model, as shown in **Table S2**. From this analysis, we obtain a simplified second-degree empirical model:

$$\begin{aligned}
 y(c_{AMPS}, c_{MBAA}, wt\%_{pAMPS}, \Phi_{pETPTA}) &= 47.7 - 8.3c_{AMPS} - 14.7c_{MBAA} - 3.4wt\%_{pAMPS} - 7.0c_{AMPS} \\
 &* c_{MBAA} - 5.9c_{AMPS} * wt\%_{pAMPS} + 8.1c_{MBAA} * \Phi_{pETPTA} + 6.3wt\%_{pAMPS} \\
 &* \Phi_{pETPTA} - 6.3c_{MBAA}^2 + 7.3wt\%_{pAMPS}^2
 \end{aligned}$$

To investigate the correlation between the experimental results and the predicted values, we use the empirical model to calculate the expected spreading factors as a function of c_{AMPS} , c_{MBAA} , $wt\%_{pAMPS}$ and Φ_{pETPTA} . Our model accurately predicts the experimentally obtained results, as shown in **Figure S4**.

The relative half-effects, calculated as $\frac{a_i}{a_0}$, determine the influence of each factor on the spreading factor. A positive sign of the relative half-effect indicates that this factor increases the spreading factor, a negative sign indicates the opposite. Our model predicts the concentration of MBAA within the pAMPS microgels to be the most influential parameter for the spreading factor: an increase of 1 wt% in the crosslinker concentration leads to a (31 ± 3) % decrease in the spreading factor, as shown in **Figure 3a**. The AMPS concentration within the drops used as template to form the pAMPS microgels also strongly influences the spreading factor of the ink: a 2.5 wt% increase in the AMPS concentration decreases the spreading factor by (17 ± 3) %. By contrast, the pETPTA microparticle size does not significantly influence the spreading factor. To minimize the clogging risk of the nozzle during the printing process and increase the printing resolution, we hence employ small pETPTA microparticles with an average diameter of (70 ± 2) μm .

Figure 3: Optimization of the spreading factor of granular inks composed of rigid pETPTA microparticles and soft pAMPS microgels. (a) Relative half-effects of the main factors (red), namely the AMPS c_{AMPS} (a_1) and MBAA c_{MBAA} (a_2) concentrations, the weight fraction of pAMPS microgels $wt\%_{pAMPS}$ (a_3), and the pETPTA diameter Φ_{pETPTA} (a_4), their interactions (blue) and the second-degree terms (purple) determined using a Box-Behnken design. This analysis reveals a strong influence of the concentrations of the monomers and crosslinker. (b)

Isosurfaces of the spreading factor of inks composed of jammed pETPTA microparticles with an average diameter of 70 μm . The color bar represents the spreading factor, where lower values indicate better printing fidelity. Optimal printing fidelity is obtained for inks containing a low weight fraction of stiff pAMPS microgels.

The DOE analysis reveals important interactions between the AMPS and MBAA concentrations, with a relative half-effect of $-(15\pm 6)\%$. Similarly, there is an interaction between the AMPS concentration and the pAMPS microgel weight fraction, with a relative half-effect of $-(12\pm 6)\%$. These negative interactions, a_{12} and a_{13} , indicate that an increase of these coupled factors leads to a stronger than expected decrease of the spreading factor. For example, if we simultaneously increase the AMPS concentration by 2.5 wt% and that of MBAA by 1 wt%, the spreading factor is 15% lower than what would be expected from an addition of the two effects. Similarly, if we simultaneously increase the AMPS concentration by 2.5 wt% and the pETPTA weight fraction from 97.2 to 98 wt%, the spreading factor decreases approximately 12% more than what would be expected by adding the individual effects. This correlation is a direct consequence of the non-linear effects of the monomer and crosslinker concentrations on the stiffness of pAMPS microgels and the weight fraction of these microgels on the rheological properties of the ink.

The ANOVA analysis indicates that the size of the rigid pETPTA microparticles does not significantly influence the rheological properties of the inks if all other parameters are kept constant, as shown in **Table S2**. By contrast, our DOE analysis reveals that the size of rigid pETPTA microparticles influences the spreading coefficient of inks, if it is simultaneously varied with the MBAA concentration within the microgels or with the pAMPS weight fraction, as indicated by the two positive interactions, a_{24} and a_{34} . Exchanging small pETPTA microparticles with large ones and simultaneously increasing the MBAA concentration by 1 wt% leads to a $(17\pm 7)\%$ increase in the spreading factor, as shown in **Figure 3a**, offsetting the decrease from the higher MBAA concentration. A similar result is observed when large pETPTA particles are replaced by bimodally distributed ones and the MBAA concentration is increased by 1 wt%. Additionally, replacing large pETPTA particles with bimodally distributed ones and simultaneously reducing the pAMPS weight fraction from 2.8 to 2 wt% results in a $(13\pm 7)\%$ increase in spreading, as shown in **Figure 3a**. We assign these effects to the polydispersity of the pETPTA microparticles: while “small” or “large” particles have a coefficient of variation (CV) below 3%, bimodally distributed particles have a CV above 50%. Our findings suggest that polydisperse stiff particles act as lubricants, thereby increasing the spreading factor of the ink."

Our experimental results reveal a non-linear response of the spreading factor with respect to the four parameters under investigation. This indication is supported by the DOE analysis that suggests important second degree coefficients a_{22} and a_{33} , with respective relative half-effects of $-(13\pm 5)\%$ and $+(15\pm 6)\%$. Taking these effects into account, our DOE analysis reveals a minimal spreading factor for inks containing a low weight fraction of stiff microgels, containing high MBAA concentrations. Yet, a microgel concentration below 2 wt% can lead to nozzle clogging during the printing, setting a lower limit to the concentration of added pAMPS

microgels. The spreading coefficient decreases with increasing microgel stiffness, which results in an increase of the printing pressure, as demonstrated in **Figure S5**. Yet, our inks do not contain any pressure sensitive substances, such that we can use stiff microgels.

Our DOE analysis reveals that the spreading factor of our ink mainly depends on the stiffness of the microgels and their weight fraction within the ink. To identify the optimum ink formulation, we plot the isosurfaces of the spreading factor for each value of the pETPTA diameter, as illustrated in **Figure 3b** and **Figure S6**. The lowest spreading factors are obtained for inks composed of small pETPTA microparticles comprising a relatively low concentration of stiff pAMPS microgels. For this reason, we select two inks with optimized compositions for the remainder of this study: Ink A is composed of 2 wt% pAMPS microgels made from a solution containing 22.5 wt% AMPS and 4 wt% MBAA. Ink B is composed of 2.2 wt% stiffer pAMPS microgels made from a solution containing 25 wt% AMPS and 3 wt% MBAA, as detailed in **Table S3**.

2.2.1. Rheological properties of the optimized inks

To assess the rheological properties of our optimized inks, we perform frequency sweeps on them. Remarkably, a weight fraction of pAMPS microgels as low as 2 wt% is sufficient to impart the ink a shear thinning behavior, as shown in **Movie S1** and **Figure 4a**. The shear thinning behavior of the ink containing 98 wt% rigid pETPTA microparticles is similar to that of inks composed of only pAMPS microgels, as shown in **Figure S7a**.^[34,36] Yet, the presence of rigid pETPTA particles increases the storage modulus of granular inks: The storage modulus of ink A in the elastic regime is (14900±400) Pa, as shown in **Figure 4b**. This value is more than three-fold higher than that of an ink solely composed of pAMPS microgels of a similar composition to that of pAMPS microgels contained in our mixed inks, which is (4370±50) Pa, as shown in **Figure S7b**. Similarly, the storage modulus of ink B in the elastic regime is (8000±100) Pa. This value is 1.5-fold higher than that of an ink composed of pAMPS microgels possessing a similar composition, which is (5280±60) Pa.

The presence of rigid particles within our inks increases their storage modulus in the elastic range. Consequently, rigid particles increase the flow point, as shown in **Figure 4b** and **Figure S7b**. For example, ink A possesses a stress at the flow point of (1900±300) Pa whereas the pETPTA microparticle-free counterpart has a stress at the flow point of (910±30) Pa. Similarly, the stress at the flow point of ink B is (1400±200) Pa whereas that of the pETPTA-free counterpart is (1070±120) Pa. Note that all flow points lie within a strain range between 15 and 30%, well suited for DIW-based 3D printing. Additionally, all the measured inks rapidly recover their storage and loss moduli, as shown in **Figure 4c** and **Figure S7c**. Hence, both optimized inks can be readily processed through DIW-based 3D printing.

The weight ratio of pETPTA microparticles and pAMPS microgels along with the jamming process involved in the formulation of the granular inks introduces variabilities in the packing density of the particles. To assess the reproducibility of the ink formulation, we quantify the spreading factor of three independently formulated identical inks. The spreading factors for inks

A and B remain consistent through the three repeats, as exemplified in **Figure 4d-e** and **Figure S8a**, indicating a good reproducibility of the ink formulations and printing.

Figure 4: Rheological properties of the optimized inks A (blue) and B (red) composed of a mixture of jammed pAMPS and pETPTA particles. (a) Angular frequency, (b) amplitude sweeps and (c) strain recovery tests performed by sequentially subjecting inks to 1% (white areas) and 100% (grey areas) strain. Ink A is composed of a mixture of 98 wt% pETPTA microparticles and 2 wt% pAMPS microgels made from a precursor solution containing 22.5 wt% AMPS and 4 wt% crosslinker (blue). Ink B is composed of 2.2 wt% pAMPS microgels and 97.8 wt% pETPTA microparticles with stiffer pAMPS microgels produced from drops containing 25 wt% AMPS and 3 wt% crosslinker (red). Photographs of printed square grids made from ink (d) A and (e) B printed at an extrusion pressure of 45 kPa and a speed of 5 mm/s. (i) Photographs (scale bar: 2 mm) and (ii) optical micrographs (scale bar: 500 μm) of the printed structure demonstrate the high printing fidelity and reveal spreading factors as low as $(20 \pm 5)\%$.

Our results suggest a homogeneous particle distribution. To test this suggestion, we visualize the granular samples using scanning electron microscopy (SEM) and confocal microscopy. Indeed, the two types of particles are homogeneously distributed within the printed structure, as illustrated in **Figure S8b**. Similarly, particles are homogeneously distributed in the cast film, as shown in **Figure S8c-d**. A reconstruction of the z-stacks acquired with confocal microscopy reveals a pAMPS volume fraction of $(61 \pm 2)\%$ for samples produced from inks A and B, as shown in **Figure S8c-d**.

2.2.2 Mechanical properties of double network granular hydrogels made from the optimized inks

Granular inks typically result in soft granular materials because of weak inter-particle interactions.^[36,37] Granular hydrogels can be stiffened if microgels are connected through a 2nd percolating hydrogel network, resulting in double network granular hydrogels.^[38–40] To test if

we can use a similar approach to rigidify our granular ink after it has been printed, we load pAMPS microgels with hydrogel precursors. We soak the optimized inks containing pAMPS microgels and pETPTA microparticles overnight in an aqueous solution containing 30 wt% acrylamide (AM), 0.5 wt% MBAA and 5 $\mu\text{L}/\text{mL}$ PI, as shown in **Figure 5a(i)-(ii)**.^[35,38,39] The dispersion is centrifuged for 10 min at 4500 rpm to concentrate the pETPTA and jam the AM-loaded pAMPS microgels, as illustrated in **Figure 5a(iii)**. We print or cast the resulting ink, as shown in **Figure 5a(iv)-(v)**. We expect the monomers to be located within the microgels and due to their diffusion along the concentration gradient also in the interstitial spaces. The structures are rigidified by polymerizing the reagents through a free radical polymerization through UV light exposure for 10 min. The printed pETPTA functionalized double network granular hydrogel (pETPTA-DNGH)-based hollow cylinder with a diameter of 1 cm can withstand more than 7000 times its own weight without being damaged, as shown in **Movie S2**.

To quantify the mechanical properties of pETPTA-DNGHs, we cast dogbone-shaped samples and perform tensile tests on them, as shown in **Figure 5b**. PETPTA-DNGHs composed of ink A display a Young's modulus of (157 ± 10) kPa, as shown in **Figure 5b**. This value is slightly above that of DNGHs composed of pAMPS microgels with a similar composition but without pETPTA particles, which is (110 ± 10) kPa (**Figure S9a**). PETPTA-DNGHs made of ink B are even stiffer with a Young's modulus of (190 ± 2) kPa, as shown in **Figure 5b**. This value is approximately 30% higher than that of pETPTA-free counterparts, as shown in **Figure S9a**. To assess if pETPTA microparticles also increase the stiffness of DNGHs under compression, we fabricate cylindrical samples for compression measurements, as shown in **Figure 5c**. Indeed, pETPTA microparticles also slightly increase the stiffness of pETPTA-DNGHs under compression: pETPTA-DNGHs made of ink A exhibit a stiffness of (400 ± 40) kPa, as shown in **Figure 5c** whereas pETPTA-free counterparts possess a stiffness of (335 ± 20) kPa, as shown in **Figure S9b**. Similarly, pETPTA-DNGHs composed of ink B display a compression modulus of (510 ± 10) kPa, as shown in **Figure 5c**, whereas pETPTA-free counterparts have a stiffness of (370 ± 15) kPa, as shown in **Figure S9b**. The difference in stiffness between pETPTA-DNGHs and their pETPTA-free counterparts is attributed to the low stiffness of pAMPS hydrogels, as shown in **Figure S10**, where bulk pAMPS exhibit a compressive modulus below 250 kPa.

Our results indicate that pETPTA particles slightly stiffen DNGHs under tension. A stiffening of any hydrogel is typically paired with a lower strain at break. The strain at break of pETPTA-DNGHs composed of inks A or B is around 140%. As expected, this value is slightly below that of their pETPTA-free counterparts, which is around 170%, as shown in **Figure S9a**. Interestingly, the fracture zone of pETPTA-DNGHs becomes white upon straining, as shown in micrographs of the dogbone samples in **Figure 5b**. We attribute this whitening to a re-arrangement of pETPTA particles that is enabled by the formation of strain-induced defects in the 2nd network. These defects enhance the mobility of the pETPTA microparticles, causing their agglomeration and the observed whitening of these regions. To better visualize this behavior, we fabricate much thinner pETPTA-DNGH films with a thickness of 250 μm comprising 2 wt% pAMPS microgels and manually stretch them, as exemplified in **Figure 5d**. We apply a lookup table transformation to the acquired time laps to highlight the color contrast

between the pETPTA microparticles (within the blue circles) and the pAMPS matrix. This analysis reveals that pETPTA microparticles comprised in as-prepared films are randomly distributed, resulting in a homogeneous appearance, as shown in **Figure 5d(i)**. If samples are strained beyond 20%, voids form around the microparticles, as highlighted by the white circles and arrows in **Figure 5d(ii)**. As the strain increases up to 50%, these voids expand, allowing the pETPTA particles to rearrange and agglomerate, as visualized in **Figure 5d(iii)**.

Figure 5: Mechanical properties of granular materials made from inks A (blue) and B (red). (a) Schematic illustration of the production of dogbone-shaped pETPTA-DNGHs made from (i) an optimized ink, which (ii) is soaked in an aqueous solution containing AM before being (iii) centrifuged to concentrate the microparticles. The resulting paste is (iv) cast and polymerized into a dogbone-shaped Teflon mold, resulting in the formation of (v) dogbones used for tensile measurements. Scale bar: 5 mm. Stress-strain curves of pETPTA-DNGHs made of inks A and B measured under (b) tension and (c) compression, from which the Young's (E_t) and compression (E_c) moduli are calculated. Inset: Photographs of 2 mm thick dogbones made from ink A before and after fracture. The whitish regions observed in the fractured dogbone correspond to areas with high pETPTA particle densities. Scale bar: 1 mm. (d) Optical

micrographs of the surface of a 250 μm thick film acquired (i) before being strained, and after having been strained to (ii) 20% and (iii) 50%. The sample is composed of small pETPTA microparticles (blue circles) with a diameter of (70 ± 2) μm and 2 wt% pAMPS microgels made from a solution containing 25 wt% monomer and 4 wt% crosslinker. At strains up to 20%, the pAMPS microgels are stretched and the porosity of the matrix increases (white circles). At higher strains up to 50%, the pETPTA particles start to rearrange, leading to the formation of regions with a high concentration of pETPTA microparticles, which appear as white areas. This strain causes the hydrogel matrix to become porous. The blue and white circles track the same two microparticles during the strain experiment. Scale bar: 80 μm .

2.3. Influence of the ink composition on the mechanical properties of double network granular hydrogels

The stiffness of DNGHs is primarily determined by that of the microgels.^[30,35,38] In pETPTA-DNGHs, the pAMPS microgels are significantly softer than the pETPTA microparticles. Therefore, we expect the stiffness of these materials to strongly depend on the weight fraction of pAMPS microgels and their intrinsic stiffness. To verify our expectation, we quantify the stiffness of pETPTA-DNGHs as a function of the pAMPS microgel weight fraction contained in them, as schematically illustrated in **Figure 6a(i)**. Remarkably, the stiffness of pETPTA-DNGHs remains constant at (220 ± 27) kPa if we increase the pAMPS microgel weight fraction from 1.7 to 5.0 wt%, as shown in **Figure 6a(ii)-(iii)** and **Figure S11a(i)**. By contrast, the stiffness of pETPTA-DNGHs increases by 370% from (47 ± 2) to (173 ± 3) kPa if we increase the MBAA concentration within the microparticles from 2 to 6 wt% to stiffen them, as shown in **Figure 6b** and **Figure S11b(i)**. As expected, the stiffness of pETPTA-DNGHs remains nearly constant around (150 ± 30) kPa if the 2nd network is stiffened by increasing the MBAA concentration within it from 0.1 to 2 wt%, as shown in **Figure 6c** and **Figure S11c(i)**.

The strain at break of DNGHs is mainly determined by that of the 2nd network^[38,39] such that we do not expect this parameter to change with the pAMPS microgel weight fraction contained in pETPTA-DNGHs. To test our expectation, we perform tensile tests on pETPTA-DNGHs containing 1.7 to 5 wt% pAMPS microgels. Indeed, their strain at break is within experimental error independent of the pAMPS weight fraction at (167 ± 10) %, as schematically shown in **Figure 6a(iii)**. Similarly, the strain at break is independent of the microgel stiffness, as shown in **Figure 6b(iii)** and **Figure S11b**. Yet, the stress at break increases from (140 ± 20) to (270 ± 40) kPa if we increase the pAMPS microgel concentration from 1.7 to 5 wt%, as shown in **Figure S11a**. We assign this behavior to the density of the 2nd network within the DNGHs that increases with increasing pAMPS microgel content as the volume of reagents used to form the 2nd network from increases. The microgel stiffness does not measurably influence the average stress at break, as shown in **Figure 6b(ii)** and **Figure S11b**. However, the error bar of the stress at break increases with increasing microgel stiffness. We assign this behavior again to the density of the 2nd network: With increasing stiffness of the microgels, their degree of swelling and therefore their ability to uptake reagents for the 2nd network decreases. As a result of the lower reagent concentration within stiffer microgels, DNGHs made from them possess a less dense 2nd network such that they are more prone to defects within this network, as illustrated in **Figure S12**.

To determine if the strain at break of our pETPTA-DNGHs is influenced by the 2nd network, as is typical for DNGHs, we vary the crosslinker concentration within the 2nd network between 0.1 and 2 wt%. Indeed, the strain at break increases by 330% from (66±13) % to (220±28) % if the MBAA concentration decreases from 2 wt% to 0.1 wt%, as shown in **Figure 6c(iii)**. We do not observe a significant influence of the MBAA concentration within the 2nd network on the stress at break, as shown in **Figure S11c(ii)**. These results indicate that the stiffness of pETPTA-DNGHs is principally determined by that of the microparticles whereas the strain at break by that of the 2nd network, well in agreement with unfunctionalized DNGHs.^[35,37]

Figure 6: Influence of the composition of inks made from soft pAMPS microgels and rigid pETPTA microparticles on the mechanical properties of pETPTA-DNGHs. Influence of the (a) weight fraction of pAMPS microgels, which is 5 (●), 3.3 (●), 2.5 (●), 2 (●) and 1.7 wt% (●), (b) crosslinker concentration in the pAMPS microgels produced from precursor solutions containing 2 (●), 3 (●), 4 (●), 5 (●) and 6 wt% (●) MBAA and (c) crosslinker concentration in the second percolating network containing 0.1 (●), 0.5 (●), 0.9 (●), 1.3 (●) and 2 wt% (●) MBAA on the (ii) stress-strain curves from which (iii) E_t (●) and the strain at break (▲) are determined. The weight fraction of pAMPS microgels does not significantly influence the

mechanical properties of pETPTA-DNGHs. By contrast, the stiffness of pETPTA-DNGHs increases with increasing microgel stiffness.

2.4. 3D printing and applications

To demonstrate the potential of our ink to fabricate structures with locally varying mechanical properties, we 3D print a caterpillar using two different inks. We employ an ink containing softer microgels to print the central part of the body (orange) and another ink containing stiffer microgels to print the front and back of the caterpillar (white), as demonstrated in **Figure 7a**. Due to the locally varying mechanical properties of the 3D printed pETPTA-DNGHs, they deform in a pre-defined fashion, as illustrated by the moving caterpillar in **Figure 7a**.

To demonstrate the potential of our mixed ink to be 3D printed into cm-sized photonic structures, we functionalize pETPTA microparticles with SiO₂ NPs of diameter of approximately 130 nm. If the concentration of SiO₂ NPs is sufficiently high, they impart the microparticles structural color, as has been previously demonstrated.^[9,12,13] Unfortunately, SiO₂ NPs strongly increase the viscosity of the ETPTA-based dispersion. To facilitate its processing through microfluidics, we add EGPEA to this dispersion to lower its viscosity, as detailed in the experimental section.^[12,13] We employ the microfluidic millipede device to produce oil-in-water drops that are converted into monodisperse photonic microparticles of diameter (110±15) μm. To obtain a blue structural color, we add approximately 13 vol% 130 nm diameter SiO₂ NPs to the acrylate-based solution, as shown in **Figure 7b**.^[31] We add 2 wt% of pAMPS microgels, made from a precursor solution containing 22.5 wt% AMPS and 4 wt% MBAA, to the colored rigid microparticles to produce an ink that possess similar rheological properties as their counterpart without SiO₂ NPs, despite changes in surface roughness, which remains at the nanometer scale, as shown in **Figure S13**. This ink can be 3D printed into a photonic triskele, as shown in **Figure 7b**.

Figure 7: 3D printing of pETPTA-DNGHs with varying mechanical and optical properties. (a) Photographs (bottom) and CAD model (top) of a 3D printed caterpillar made from 15 layers of an ink composed of pETPTA microparticles and soft (orange area) or stiff (white areas) pAMPS microgels. Due to the locally varying mechanical properties, the caterpillar deforms in a pre-defined fashion, allowing it to advance. Scale bar: 1.5 cm. (b) (i) CAD model and (ii) photograph of a 3D printed photonic triskele made from 2 layers of an ink composed of pAMPS microgels and pETPTA/pEGPEA microparticles comprising 13 vol% 130 nm diameter SiO₂ NPs. The microparticles of diameter (110±15) μm display blue structural color. Scale bar: 0.5 cm. (iii) Optical micrograph of a zoom in of the triskele, revealing the bright blue pETPTA microparticles. Scale bar: 0.4 mm.

2.5. Alternatives towards industrial use

The brightness of photonic microparticles increases with increasing volume fraction of SiO₂ NPs contained in them. Yet, the viscosity of NP containing dispersions strongly increases with increasing NP concentration. This increase in viscosity hampers the controlled processing of the dispersions through microfluidics: the microfluidic millipede device enables processing dispersions with viscosities up to 155 mPa.s into drops of controlled sizes.^[41] This requirement sets an upper limit to the SiO₂ NP concentration within the monodisperse photonic microparticles. To overcome this limitation, we fabricate polydisperse photonic microparticles through batch emulsification. A viscous ETPTA/SiO₂ dispersion containing up to 33 vol% SiO₂ NPs is emulsified with an aqueous solution containing pluronic as a surfactant through vortexing, as shown in **Figure 8a**. The resulting polydisperse drops with diameters ranging from 10 to 110 μm are converted into photonic microparticles by exposing them to UV light for 5 min, as shown in **Figure 8b-c**. The photonic microparticles are mixed with soft pAMPS microgels with diameters ranging from 5 to 40 μm before being concentrated and 3D printed,

as schematically shown in **Figure 8d**. Note that the photonic microparticles and microgels are produced from emulsion drops made through batch emulsification such that their diameters are similar.

To demonstrate the potential of the ink, we 3D print butterflies using two different inks. Both inks contain 2.2 wt% pAMPS microgels and 97.8 wt% pETPTA-SiO₂ microparticles. The first ink contains microparticles functionalized with 150 nm diameter SiO₂ NPs that display a blue structural color. The second ink contains microparticles functionalized with 180 nm SiO₂ NPs that display a bright green structural color, as illustrated in **Figure 8e**. These structural colors arise from the self-assembly of SiO₂ NPs within pETPTA, resulting in periodic nanostructures close to the microparticle surface, as exemplified in **Figure S14a-b**. We rigidify the 3D printed butterflies by exposing them to UV light to initiate the free radical polymerization of the reagents contained within the microgels to form a 2nd percolating network. The resulting butterflies are mechanically stable yet flexible, as demonstrated in **Figure S14c**. The structural colors arise if the butterfly is soaked in water and placed on a black background, preventing unwanted light scattering, as shown in **Figure S14d**. The butterfly exhibits a reflection peak of up to 35% in the blue and green regions, as shown in **Figure 8e(ii)** and **Figure S15b-c**. This reflection peak is approximately 10% less intense than that of pure photonic microparticles. We attribute the decreased reflectance peak intensity to the presence of pAMPS microgels within the printed butterfly that do not contribute to the structural colors. Due to the isotropic nature of the spherical photonic microparticles, the 3D printed butterfly does not exhibit iridescence, as demonstrated in **Figure S15**.

Figure 8: Schematic illustration of the production of photonic polydisperse particles and their formulation into an ink. (a) A dispersion containing ETPTA monomers and 33 vol% of SiO₂ NPs is emulsified in water via vortexing, (b) resulting in polydisperse oil-in-water drops. (c) Drops are converted into stiff photonic microparticles by illuminating them with UV light to initiate the free radical polymerization. The blue microparticles are made using 150 nm diameter SiO₂ nanoparticles, while the green microparticles contain 180 nm diameter SiO₂ nanoparticles. Scale bars: 100 μm. Inset: Reflectance measurement of the photonic microparticles in specular mode, showing a strong reflectance around 470 nm and 560 nm, respectively. (d) Stiff pETPTA microparticles are mixed with soft pAMPS microgels and concentrated to form a 3D printable ink. (e) (i) Photograph of a 3D coprinted butterfly made from 2 layers of inks composed of 97.8 wt% photonic pETPTA microparticles displaying blue and green colors, and 2.2 wt% pAMPS microgels made from 25 wt% AMPS and 3 wt% MBAA. Scale bar: 500 μm. (ii) Optical micrographs of a blue region (zone 1) and a green region (zone 2) of the coprinted butterfly. Scale bars: 50 μm. Inset: the corresponding reflectance spectra.

To demonstrate the potential of our photonic microparticles as optical sensor, we replace pAMPS microgels with temperature-responsive poly(*N*-isopropylacrylamide) (pNIPAM) microfragments, as shown in **Figure S16**. To increase the temperature sensitivity, we substitute the pAM percolating network with pNIPAM. This temperature-responsive polymer has a lower

critical solution temperature (LCST) around 30-35°C.^[42-45] Below the LCST, pNIPAM is hydrophilic and transparent. Above the LCST, it collapses, rendering it translucent, as exemplified in **Figure S16c**. We formulate an ink containing photonic pETPTA microparticles, containing 33 vol% SiO₂ NPs of diameter 150 nm or 180 nm, that are mixed with the thermo-responsive pNIPAM microfragments at a weight ratio of 1:10, as illustrated in **Figure 9a(i)**. The ink is soaked in a NIPAM-containing precursor solution before the microparticles and microfragments are jammed and cast into 2 mm tall cylinders, as schematically illustrated in **Figure 9a(ii)-(iv)**. At room temperature, the cylinders exhibit bright green and blue structural colors due to the high transparency of pNIPAM fragments, as shown in **Figure 9b(i)** and **Figure S17a**. If heated to 36°C, the degree of hydration of the pNIPAM-based photonic devices decreases by approximately 25%, such that they become translucent. This change in optical appearance results in a reduction in the overall brightness of the photonic cylinders, as shown in **Figure 9b(ii)-c** and **Figure S17b-c**, with a 10% decrease in the reflectance peak intensity upon heating. If the temperature is again decreased below the LCST of pNIPAM, the photonic sensors return to their initial state, exhibiting bright green and blue colors, indicating the reversibility of the process. Note that the recovery of the initial optical properties occurs within a few minutes after cooling, as shown in **Figure 9c** and **Figure S17b-c**. Because of the processability, good mechanical and optical properties and the flexibility in the material choice, we deem this material to be well-suited for the next generation of biomedical sensors and anticounterfeiting labels.

Figure 9: Thermo-responsive photonic granular material. (a) Schematic illustration of the fabrication of thermo-responsive photonic DNGHs. (i) The ink is made of 90 wt% photonic pETPTA microparticles and 10 wt% temperature-responsive pNIPAM microfragments. (ii) The microparticles and microfragments are soaked in a NIPAM-containing precursor solution, (iii)

jammed, (iv) and molded before the reagents are polymerized. The photonic microparticles contain 33 vol% SiO₂ NPs with a diameter of 150 nm resulting in a blue color or 180 nm resulting in a green color. (b) Photographs of the photonic devices at (i) 23°C, and (ii) 36°C. At room temperature, the devices exhibit bright green or blue colors. Above 35°C, these colors fade due to a lower degree of hydration of pNIPAM, which renders it translucent. By returning to 23°C, the structural colors regain their brightness because pNIPAM again becomes nearly transparent, demonstrating the reversible nature of our thermo-responsive materials. Scale bars: 4 mm (top) and 1 mm (bottom). c) Reflectance spectra of the photonic sensors taken at 23°C (dark colors) and 36°C (light colors), demonstrating a significant decrease of the reflectance peak intensity when the temperature increases from 23 to 36°C.

3. Conclusion

We introduce a granular ink composed of a mixture of rigid photonic pETPTA microparticles and soft pAMPS microgels that can be 3D printed into cm-sized structures possessing locally varying mechanical and optical properties. We demonstrate that the printing fidelity mainly depends on the stiffness of the pAMPS microgels and their weight fraction within the ink. We rigidify the granular structure by loading the microgels with hydrogel precursors that can be polymerized after the ink has been processed into the appropriate shape. Thereby, we form a 2nd hydrogel network that interpenetrates the microgels and covalently links them, resulting in mechanically stable pETPTA-DNGHs. The stiffness of these materials is mainly determined by the pETPTA weight fraction and the stiffness of the microgels. By contrast, the strain at break of these materials mainly depends on that of the 2nd network such that these two parameters can be independently tuned. We demonstrate the potential of this ink to produce self-supporting granular materials possessing locally varying mechanical properties by co-3D printing two inks. Similarly, by replacing the pAMPS microgels with pNIPAM fragments, we render the granular photonic structure thermo-responsive. We foresee this ink to enable the fabrication of cm-sized mechanically stable and durable yet deformable materials that can be used for counterfeiting applications, as smart sensors and for visually appealing moving structures.

4. Experimental Section/Methods

Materials: Ethoxylated trimethylolpropane triacrylate (ETPTA) (Sigma-Aldrich, 409073, MW = 428 g/mol), Pluronic F127 Prill (BASF, 51181981), poly(ethylene glycol) phenyl ether acrylate (pEGPEA) (Sigma Aldrich, 56641-05-5, MW = 324 g/mol), 2-hydroxy-2-methylpropiophenone (PI) (Sigma-Aldrich, 405655), SiO₂ NPs (Sukgyung AT, Korea), mineral oil light (Sigma-Aldrich, 330779), poly(N-isopropylacrylamide) (pNIPAM) (abcr, 2210-25-5, MW = 113 g/mol), span 80 (TCI America, 1338438), 2-acrylamido-2-methyl-1-propanesulfonic acid (AMPS) (Sigma-Aldrich, 282731, MW = 207.25 g/mol), MBAA (Carl Roth, 203-750-9, MW = 154.17 g/mol), acrylamide (AM) 30% (Thermo Fisher, 79-06-1, MW = 71.08 g/mol), poly(dimethylsiloxane) (PDMS) (Sylgard 184, Dow Chemical Company, USA), dimethylsiloxane-(60-70% Ethylene Oxide) block copolymer (PDMS-PEG) (Cymit Quimica, 27306-78-1, 20 cSt), poly(diallyldimethylammonium chloride) (PolyDADMAC)

(Sigma Aldrich, 409030, MW = 400 000-500 000 g/mol), sodium Chloride (NaCl) (Acros organics, 7647-14-5, MW = 58.44 g/mol), tetramethylrhodamine isothiocyanate-Dextran (TRITC-dextran) (Sigma Aldrich, 3107414, MW = 155 kg/mol) are used as received.

Preparation of Microfluidic Devices: Patterned wafers are produced through soft photolithography in a clean room environment before being used as molds to produce microfluidic millipede devices made from PDMS formed by mixing the elastomer and curing agent at a weight ratio of 10:1. The patterned PDMS is oxygen plasma treated for about 30 s and bonded onto a glass slide (Gala Instrumente, Plasma Prep 2). To produce O/W drops, the surfaces of the millipede device must be hydrophilic. We surface modify the PDMS using an aqueous solution containing 2 wt% PolyDADMAC and 1 M NaCl.^[46] After 30 min of incubation, we remove the solution from the channels using deionized (DI) water and use the device within a day of the surface treatment. We produce small particles with a diameter of about 70 μm from devices with a nozzle height $h = 20 \mu\text{m}$ and large particles of about 130 μm in diameter from devices with a nozzle height $h = 40 \mu\text{m}$.^[20]

Photonic microparticles used to print the triskele are made from a dispersion composed of ETPTA, EGPEA (50/50 wt%) and 13 vol% SiO₂ NPs of diameter about 130 nm^[31] using a millipede device with $h = 40 \mu\text{m}$. To improve the hydrophilicity of the device, 0.5 wt% of PDMS-PEG is added to the precursor solution containing PDMS^[47] After the plasma bonding, the channels are immersed for 30 min in a polyelectrolyte solution. The channels are washed with DI water and stored in water, such that the unpolymerized PEG chains contained in the PDMS device migrate to the surface of the channels, resulting in an improved hydrophilicity.

Production of the Photonic Dispersion: Photonic dispersions used to produce the polydisperse photonic microparticles are prepared following previously published protocols.^[13,18] Prior to use, the purchased SiO₂ NPs, of diameter 130, 150 and 180 nm, are dispersed in ethanol and centrifuged three times to improve their monodispersity. The NPs are dried in a convection oven at 80°C and redispersed in ethanol for several hours. A precise amount of ETPTA and 1 wt% of PI is added to the dispersion to achieve the desired volume fraction of SiO₂ NPs. The ethanol is evaporated using a convection oven at 80°C and the dispersion is stored at 4 °C, shielded from light.

To prepare the dispersion for use in the millipede device, we mix EGPEA and ETPTA monomers at a weight ratio of 1:1, along with 1 wt% of PI, before combining with the SiO₂ dispersed in ethanol. The addition of EGPEA reduces the overall viscosity of the dispersion, facilitating its use in microfluidics devices.

Preparation of the pAMPS Microgels: Unless specified otherwise, the pAMPS microgels are formed by emulsifying an aqueous solution containing 22.5 wt% AMPS, 3 wt% MBAA and 1 $\mu\text{L}/\text{mL}$ PI with a mineral oil-based solution containing 2 wt% span 80 at a volume ratio 1:3. We emulsify the two solutions within three cycles of vortexing of 30 s each, at 2500 rpm. The reagents contained within the drops are polymerized by exposing them to UV light for 5 min (OmniCure LX500, Excelitas Technologies, at 240 mW/cm², 365 nm). To ensure homogeneous polymerization, we disperse the drops in a 50 mL beaker and stir them at 400

rpm.^[30] The resulting microgels are washed three times in mineral oil and three times in DI water before being freeze dried for several days.

Preparation of the pETPTA Microparticles: The pETPTA microparticles are produced in a PDMS millipede device with hydrophilic surfaces by emulsifying an ETPTA-based precursor solution containing 1 wt% PI with a DI water-based solution encompassing 1 wt% of pluronic that we use as a surfactant. To produce the small pETPTA particles, we use a millipede device with a nozzle height of 20 μm , where the flow rate for the inner phase is typically 1 mL/h, and that of the outer phase is 5 mL/h. Large pETPTA particles are produced from millipede devices with a nozzle height of 40 μm . The inner phase is injected at 2 mL/h, the outer phase at 10 mL/h. Drops are converted into microparticles by illuminating them with UV light for 1 min (OmniCure LX500, Excelitas Technologies, at 240 mW/cm², 365 nm) to initiate the free radical polymerization reaction of the reagents contained within them. To ensure a homogeneous polymerization and avoid the eventual formation of agglomerates, we stir during the polymerization at 300 rpm. The resulting particles are washed five times with DI water and freeze dried for several days.

Preparation of the pETPTA Photonic Microparticles: Polydisperse photonic microparticles are produced by vortexing 1.5 mL of an ETPTA-based dispersion containing 33 vol% of silica NPs of diameter 150 or 180 nm in 5 mL of an aqueous solution containing 1 wt% of pluronic for 30s at 2500 rpm. Subsequently, the drops are polymerized under UV light for 5 min (OmniCure LX500, Excelitas Technologies, at 240 mW/cm², 365 nm) while being stirred at 300 rpm. The microparticles are washed five times with DI water before being freeze dried for several days.

Monodisperse photonic microparticles are produced using the PDMS-based millipede device functionalized with PDMS-PEG block copolymer. A dispersion containing ETPTA and EGPEA at a volume ratio of 1:1 and 13 vol% SiO₂ NPs with a diameter of approximately 130 nm are emulsified in a water-based solution containing 1 wt% of pluronic. The height of the millipede nozzle is $h = 40 \mu\text{m}$, with the flow rates of the inner and outer phases typically at 0.2 mL/h and 7 mL/h, respectively. The reagents contained in drops are polymerized under UV light for 5 min (OmniCure LX500, Excelitas Technologies, at 240 mW/cm², 365 nm) to obtain photonic microbeads with a diameter of (110 \pm 20) μm . The resulting particles are washed five times in DI water and freeze dried for several days.

Preparation of the Temperature-Sensitive Photonic Device: Bulk pNIPAM hydrogel is produced by polymerizing an aqueous precursor solution containing 15 wt% NIPAM, 1 wt% MBAA and 1 wt% PI for 10 min using a CAMAG UV lamp (366nm, 2.2 mW/cm²). Fragmentation is performed with a commercial cryomiller (CryoMill, Retsch) using a 10 mm stainless steel ball, involving a precooling cycle at -196°C followed by milling at 30 Hz for 2 min. The resulting pNIPAM fragments, with diagonals ranging from 10 to 600 μm , are freeze-dried to obtain a powder, facilitating the control over pNIPAM:pETPTA ratio. To prepare the mixed ink at a 1:10 ratio, 0.1 g of pNIPAM microfragments is mixed with 1 g of pETPTA microparticles. This mixture is soaked overnight in a solution containing 15 wt% of NIPAM, 1 wt% MBAA and 1 $\mu\text{L/mL}$ PI. The soaked ink is filtered and cast into a cylindrical 2 mm tall

Teflon mold before being UV polymerized for 5 min (CAMAG UV lamp, 366nm, 2.2 mW/cm²), forming a photonic pETPTA-pNIPAM temperature-responsive DN.

Formulation of the Granular Ink: To prepare the ink with the desired weight fraction of pAMPS microgels, a known amount of dried pAMPS microgels is swollen in DI water. A known amount of pETPTA particles is mixed with the swollen pAMPS microgel suspension. For example, an ink containing 2 wt% dried pAMPS microgels is prepared by adding 5 g of pETPTA microparticles to 0.1 g of pAMPS microgels. 10 mL of ethanol is added to prevent the formation of agglomerates in the ink. The mixture is soaked for 5 min before being centrifuged for 10 min at 2300 g (Mega Star 1.6R, VWR) to remove the excess of water and ethanol. To introduce the second percolating network, the prepared ink is soaked overnight in an aqueous solution containing 30 wt% AM, 0.5 wt% MBAA, and 5 μ L/mL PI.^[35] The ink is filtered before it is filled into a 3 mL syringe, which is centrifuged for 1 min at 4500 rpm to remove air bubbles.

DOE Analysis: A Box-Behnken design with three central points ($N_0 = 3$), chosen for its cost-effectiveness, is used to model the spreading factor of each ink composed of pETPTA microparticles mixed with pAMPS microgels as a function of the AMPS (a_1) and MBAA concentrations (a_2) in the pAMPS microgels, the weight fraction of pAMPS microgels in the ink (a_3) and the pETPTA microparticle diameter (a_4). The 27 experiments are performed in a stochastic order to minimize random errors, such as those resulting from variations in temperature and humidity. From the experimental results, we then calculate a second-degree empirical model, $y(x) = a_0 + \sum_{i=1}^4 a_i x_i + \sum_{i < j}^4 a_{ij} x_i x_j$, which relates the printing fidelity to the four processing parameters. The 15 coefficients a_i and a_{ij} describe the effect of each factor x_i on the spreading factor of the inks, whereas the constant a_0 describes the effect of the factors that are kept constant, such as the printing speed and temperature, on the spreading factor. To calculate the coefficients a_i from the empirical model, we use the least square fit algorithm. The model's statistical validity is confirmed through ANOVA analysis and the coefficients with a high pValue, indicating high uncertainty attributed to experimental error, are discarded. Since our experiments include errors related to variations in the ink preparation and jamming process, strongly influencing the ink rheology, we kept all coefficients with a pValue below 15%. We calculate the error on each relative half-effect with a confidence interval at 90%. To fit the obtained second-degree model in our experimental space, a canonical analysis is performed and the fixed point, eigenvectors and eigenvalues are calculated. The isosurfaces are 3D plotted using the *patch* and *isosurface* functions on MATLAB for each value of the pETPTA microparticle diameter considered.

Preparation of the Samples for Universal Testing Machine (UTM): The inks are soaked overnight in an AM-containing precursor solution at a ratio 1:1 (microgels:AM solution). The excess of the AM-containing solution is removed through centrifugation and filtration before the ink is cast into a dogbone or cylinder-shaped Teflon mold. To crosslink the pAMPS microgels and thereby obtain pETPTA-DNGH samples, the granular inks are exposed to UV light for 5 to 10 min (CAMAG UV lamp, 366nm, 2.2 mW/cm²) to initiate the free radical polymerization of the reagents contained within the microgels. The dogbone-shaped samples, designed for tensile measurements, have a cross-section of 5 mm in width and 2 mm in

thickness, whereas the cylindrical samples, designed for compression tests, are 8.5 mm in diameter and 5 mm in height. All samples are soaked in water over night before being tested with UTM.

3D Printing of the Granular Ink: The granular mixed inks are centrifuged to concentrate the microparticles into a jammed state. The vast majority of the top layer, corresponding to excess liquid, is removed using a pipette. To remove the remaining excess liquid, we transfer the two layers of densely packed microparticles onto a 7 μm mesh paper filter (Whatman, diameter 110 mm, WH989410103). We mix the two populations of densely packed particles with a spatula to ensure a homogeneous ink. The ink is loaded into 3 mL syringes. If needed, the syringes are centrifuged at 3000 rpm for 1 min to eliminate air bubbles and ensure a proper filling. Note that this centrifugation does not cause any phase separation between the stiff pETPTA microparticles and soft pAMPS microgels because the particles are too densely packed at this stage. A commercial pneumatic 3D printer (BIO XTM 3D printer, Cellink) with a conical 22G nozzle (410 μm in diameter) is used to quantify the spreading factor of granular inks. The printing process is performed at room temperature, with a gap between the nozzle and the printing pad set to 0.3 mm. The polymerization of the percolating network in the printed structures is triggered by UV illuminating the structure for about 5 min (CAMAG UV lamp, 366nm, 2.2 mW/cm²). To print more intricate structures, such as the rock-hand, we introduce polymerization steps during the printing process, by exposing the samples every 5 printed layers to UV light for 15 s. This procedure ensures that the base of the structure remains stable and does not collapse under its own weight. In this example, the pAMPS microgels are made from a solution containing 22.5 wt% AMPS and 4 wt% MBAA. The green and blue butterfly is printed from a conical 22G nozzle (410 μm) at 3-4 mm/s and 20 kPa. For the caterpillar, we use an ink composed of soft pAMPS microgels made from a solution containing 22.5 wt% AMPS and 2 wt% MBAA while the stiff pAMPS microgels are made from a solution containing 25 wt% AMPS and 4 wt% MBAA. The pAMPS weight fraction, pETPTA microparticle diameter and composition of the second percolating network are kept constant. A conical 22G nozzle (410 μm) with a printing speed of 5 mm/s is used. The printing pressure varies with the ink: The soft mixed ink is printed at 20 kPa (orange) while the stiffer mixed ink is printed at 45 kPa (white).

Measurement of the Printing Fidelity: For each granular ink, a minimum of three square grids of 10x10 mm² are printed at 5 mm/s with a conical 22G nozzle and optical microscope images are taken. The printing fidelity is quantified with the spreading factor, calculated as $\frac{|A_{exp}-A_{th}|}{A_{th}} * 100$ (%), where A_{exp} is the average area inside the printed squares measured with ImageJ and A_{th} is the theoretical area that would be obtained if the ink is not spreading. Ideally, this number should be minimal to optimize the printing resolution.

Measurement of the Hydration Degree: To quantify the change in the degree of hydration of the temperature-sensitive photonic cylinders upon changes in temperature, we measure their volumes at room temperature and 36°C using optical micrographs. The degree of

hydration is calculated as: $\frac{|V_{RT}-V_{36^{\circ}C}|}{V_{36^{\circ}C}} * 100$ (%), where V_{RT} and $V_{36^{\circ}C}$ represent the volumes of the photonic devices measured at room temperature and at 36°C, respectively.

Characterization of the Microparticles and Microparticle-based Materials: All the produced microparticles are imaged with a Nikon optical microscope and the captured images are analyzed using ImageJ. This procedure enables the estimation of an average particle size and polydispersity based on the measurement of at least 30 particles. For the photonic microparticles, we used an optical microscope in reflection mode (Eclipse L150, Nikon) to take images. The homogeneity of the printed filament containing pAMPS microgels and pETPTA microparticles is verified using a Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM) (Gemini, Carl Zeiss, Germany) operated at 3 keV with a working distance of 5.5 mm acquired with a secondary electron detector. To avoid charging effects, the samples are coated with a 10 nm thick iridium layer (Q150, Quorum Technologies, UK). For the photonic microparticles, we cleaved them using a razor blade, coated them with Platinum, and imaged their cross-sections using SEM (SU8230, Hitachi).

Measurement of the pAMPS volume fraction in the final pETPTA-based DNGHs: Films with a thickness of approximately 120 μm are observed under a confocal microscope (Leica SP8) equipped with a 16x oil immersion objective to evaluate the average volume fraction of pAMPS microgels. For this purpose, pAMPS microgels are stained with TRITC-dextran (1 mg per 1 g of microgels), and a z-stack over about 80 μm is performed, using a z-step size of 0.6 μm . We use a 552 nm laser and the signal is detected between 560 and 600 nm. Each measurement is repeated three times for each sample, and the pAMPS volume percent is determined using Fiji based on the measurements from three distinct samples.

Rheological Properties of the Jammed Granular Inks: All rheological measurements are performed with a DHR-3 TA Instrument operated at room temperature in the oscillation mode. The granular inks are centrifuged for 10 min at 4500 rpm and filtered to remove the excess water. The inks are deposited onto a 8 mm diameter parallel plate geometry, ensuring a gap height of 500 μm . The amplitude sweep measurements are performed at an angular frequency of 1 rad/s whereas the frequency sweeps measurements are performed at 0.4% strain. The self-healing test is measured at 1 rad/s and is composed of nine cycles of 200 s where the strain is alternated between 1% and 100%.

Mechanical Properties of the mixed DNGHs: The pETPTA-DNGHs, cast into dogbones or cylinders, are measured with a UTM (zwickiLine 5 kN, 50 N load cell, Zwick Roell). In the tensile mode, pneumatic clamps are used to mount the dogbones, with a typical pressure between 2 and 2.5 bar. Tensile and compression tests are conducted at a constant speed of 100 mm/min with a preload of 0.05 N and are repeated four times for each batch. The stiffness, stress at break and strain at break are obtained from the stress-strain curves and averaged over at least three samples. The Young's modulus, taken as the average slope in the linear elastic region between 5 and 15% of strain, are systematically calculated using MATLAB.

Reflectance Properties of the Printed Photonic Structures: The reflectance spectra were obtained using a fiber-coupled spectrometer (HR4000CG-UV–NIR, Ocean Optics) paired with a tungsten halogen light source (HL-2000-HP, Ocean Insight). The reflectance spectra were normalized using a diffuse reflectance standard (SRS-99-010, Labsphere, Inc.).

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Supporting Information

3D PRINTING OF STIFF LOAD-BEARING PHOTONIC MICROPARTICLES

*Pauline Pradal, Paul Hardivillé, Jong Bin Kim, Seong Kyeong Nam, Shin-Hyun Kim, Esther Amstad**

Movie S1: 2D extrusion-based printing of a 10x10 mm² square grid from an ink composed of large pETPTA particles and 2 wt% pAMPS microgels made from a solution containing 22.5 wt% monomer and 4 wt% crosslinker. The printing process operates with a nozzle of inner diameter of 410 μm , a printing pressure of 20 kPa and a printing speed of 5 mm/s. Scale bar: 5 mm.

Movie S2: Compression test of a 3D printed hollow cylinder made from ink A that is loaded with a 1 kg weight, demonstrating the deformability and mechanical stability of our granular material. Scale bar: 1 cm.

Figure S1: Rheological properties of densely packed pETPTA microparticles. (a) Amplitude and (b) angular frequency sweeps measured on an ink composed of pETPTA microparticles of diameter $(130 \pm 3) \mu\text{m}$, produce with a millipede device where $h = 40 \mu\text{m}$. Despite their shear-thinning behavior, the yield point, determined by the crossover of G' and G'' , occurs at (600 ± 50) kPa and falls beyond the printability window of commercial extrusion printers, resulting in nozzle clogging.

Figure S2: PAMPS microgels and pETPTA microparticles used to assess the influence of their size ratio on the granular ink printability. Optical micrographs of (a) pAMPS microgels obtained by emulsifying a solution containing 20 wt% AMPS and 4 wt% MBAA with a millipede device where $h = 10 \mu\text{m}$. The resulting microgels have a diameter of $(117 \pm 7) \mu\text{m}$. Optical micrographs of pETPTA microparticles with a diameter (b) of $(70 \pm 2) \mu\text{m}$ obtained using a millipede device with $h = 20 \mu\text{m}$ and (c) ranging from 10 to $70 \mu\text{m}$ obtained by vortexing. Optical micrographs of (d) pAMPS microgels obtained by vortexing a solution containing 25 wt% AMPS and 3 wt% MBAA, resulting in microgels with a diameter ranging from 5 to $40 \mu\text{m}$ and (e) pETPTA microparticles with a diameter of $(130 \pm 3) \mu\text{m}$ obtained using a millipede device with $h = 40 \mu\text{m}$. Scale bars: $150 \mu\text{m}$.

Table S1: Set of the 27 experiments given by a Box-Behnken design with 3 central points. This three-level design allows to optimize the printing fidelity by adjusting the 4 processing factors we study: c_{AMPS} (a_1) and c_{MBAA} (a_2) in the solution the microgels are made from, the weight fraction of pAMPS microgels in the ink $\text{wt}\%_{\text{pAMPS}}$ (a_3) and the diameter of pETPTA particles $\varnothing_{\text{pETPTA}}$ (a_4). By using the least square fit algorithm on the spreading factor which characterizes the printing fidelity of each ink, this design allows the identification of the main coefficients a_i , the interaction coefficients a_{ij} and the second-degree coefficients a_{ii} representing the effects of the factors x_i on the spreading factor of the inks in a second-degree model with interactions:

$$y(x) = a_0 + \sum_{i=1}^4 a_i x_i + \sum_{i < j}^4 a_{ij} x_i x_j.$$

Experiment	C_{AMPS} (wt%)	C_{MBAA} (wt%)	pAMPS (wt%)	∅_{pETPTA} (μm)
1	20	3	5	large
2	20	3	2	large
3	25	3	5	large
4	25	3	2	large
5	22.5	2	2.8	small
6	22.5	2	2.8	mixture
7	22.5	4	2.8	small
8	22.5	4	2.8	mixture
9	20	3	2.8	small
10	20	3	2.8	mixture
11	25	3	2.8	small
12	25	3	2.8	mixture
13	22.5	2	5	large
14	22.5	4	5	large
15	22.5	2	2	large
16	22.5	4	2	large
17	20	2	2.8	large
18	20	4	2.8	large
19	25	2	2.8	large
20	25	4	2.8	large
21	22.5	3	5	small
22	22.5	3	5	mixture
23	22.5	3	2	small
24	22.5	3	2	mixture
25	22.5	3	2.8	large
26	22.5	3	2.8	large
27	22.5	3	2.8	large

Figure S3: (a) Optical micrograph of a single square printed from an ink composed of large pETPTA microparticles mixed with 2.8 wt% pAMPS microgels made from an aqueous solution containing 25 wt% AMPS and 4 wt% MBAA, showing the theoretical (A_{th}) and experimental (A_{exp}) square areas used to calculate the spreading factor. Scale bar: 500 μm . (b) Summary of the results of the 27 experiments showing the spreading factor as a function of the printing pressure. Inks are composed of mixtures of pAMPS microgels with different compositions and pETPTA microparticles of different diameters. The spreading factors are quantified from optical microscopy images and averaged over at least 3 square grids of 4 single squares. As expected, the printing pressure increases with decreasing spreading factors.

Table S2: Verification of the statistical validity of the empirical model obtained from DOE. The ANOVA table of the final second-degree model confirms the validity of each coefficient displaying a pValue smaller than 12%. The selection of this rather high boundary pValue is made with the awareness that, in this study, the experimental error can be high because of variations in the degree of jamming of microparticles, which influence the rheological properties of the inks.

	SS	DF	MS	F	pValue
a_1	820.78	1	820.78	15.99	9.3×10^{-4}
a_2	2592.42	1	2592.42	50.50	1.7×10^{-6}
a_3	140.47	1	140.47	2.74	1.2×10^{-1}
a_{12}	196.37	1	196.37	3.82	6.7×10^{-2}
a_{13}	139.49	1	139.49	2.72	1.2×10^{-1}
a_{24}	262.89	1	262.89	5.12	3.7×10^{-2}
a_{34}	158.92	1	158.92	3.10	9.7×10^{-2}
a_{22}	349.27	1	349.27	6.80	1.8×10^{-2}
a_{33}	250.25	1	250.25	4.87	4.1×10^{-2}
error	872.81	17	51.34	1	5.0×10^{-1}

Figure S4: Comparison of spreading factors estimated from the empirical model and those obtained from experimental data. (a) Results of the 27 experiments performed by tuning the four processing factors: c_{AMPS} , c_{MBAA} , $wt\%_{pAMPS}$ and ϕ_{pETPTA} . Experimental data (green) is compared with predicted values from the empirical model (brown), showing a good correlation and spreading factors spanning from 20% to 70%. Influence of the concentrations of (b) AMPS and (c) MBAA within the microgels, (d) weight fraction of pAMPS and (e) pETPTA particle diameter on the spreading factors. The model predicts that increasing the concentrations of AMPS and MBAA significantly reduces the spreading factor, while the pAMPS weight fraction has a minimal impact. Increasing the pETPTA diameter and polydispersity slightly increases the spreading factor, supporting the use of small pETPTA microparticles.

Figure S5: Influence of the pAMPS microgel weight fraction within the mixed ink on its 3D printability. Photographs of printed square grids made from inks containing large pETPTA microparticles mixed with (a) 1.25 wt%, (b) 1.5 wt% and (c) 2 wt% pAMPS microgels initially made from a solution containing 22.5 wt% AMPS and 4 wt% MBAA. Scale bars: 2 mm. As the pAMPS weight fraction increases, the printing pressure decreases: it is 65 kPa for inks containing 1.5 wt% pAMPS and 20 kPa for inks containing 2 wt% pAMPS. The higher the weight fraction of pETPTA, the higher is the printing pressure and fidelity. Inset: Example of optical micrographs of a zoom-in of a single printed square from which the spreading factors were calculated. The spreading factor is (b) (21 ± 3) % and (c) (29 ± 5) %. Scale bars: 500 μm .

Figure S6: Results of the optimization using a Box-Behnken design. Isosurfaces of the spreading factor for pETPTA microparticles with (a) a diameter around 130 μm and (b) a bimodal size distribution where diameters range from 70 to 130 μm . The best printing fidelity (dark blue area) is obtained for high concentrations of AMPS and MBAA within the drops used to make pAMPS microgels and for low percentages of pAMPS microgels with respect to pETPTA microparticles in the ink. This optimal area is largest for inks composed of small pETPTA microparticles. For this reason, this study is conducted on mixed inks composed of small pETPTA microparticles with an average diameter of 70 μm .

Table S3: Parameters used to fabricate the two optimized inks A (blue) and B (red). To maximize the printing fidelity, we maximize the AMPS and MBAA concentrations in drops used as templates to produce pAMPS microgels and minimize the weight fraction of pAMPS microgels with respect to pETPTA microparticles. Small pETPTA microparticles of about 70 μm in diameter are used for these two inks.

<i>Ink</i>	c_{AMPS} (wt%)	c_{MBAA} (wt%)	pAMPS (wt%)	ϕ_{pETPTA} (μm)
A	22.5	4	2	small
B	25	3	2.2	small

Figure S7: Rheological properties of jammed pAMPS microgels. (a) Angular frequency and (b) amplitude sweeps measured on inks composed of pAMPS microgels possessing similar compositions as those used for our optimized mixed granular inks A and B. These pAMPS microgels are produced from an aqueous solution containing 22.5 wt% AMPS and 4 wt% MBAA (light blue) or from an aqueous solution containing 25 wt% AMPS and 3 wt% MBAA (light red).

Figure S8: Reproducibility of the printing of the optimized inks. (a) Optimized inks A and B possess a spreading factor below 25% and an extrusion pressure between 45 and 65 kPa. Measurements are repeated on three independent inks. (b) Scanning electron microscopy image of a printed structure composed of 2 wt% pAMPS microgels mixed with pETPTA microparticles displaying a homogeneous distribution of the microparticles within the interpenetrating network. Scale bar: 100 μm . Confocal microscopy images of inks (c) A and (d) B used to determine the volume fraction of pAMPS microgels within the final material. In both cases, the volume fraction of pAMPS microgels is $(61 \pm 2)\%$. Scale bar: 50 μm .

Figure S9: Stress-strain curves of DNGHs made of pAMPS microgels under (a) tension and (b) compression. The light blue curves correspond to pAMPS microgels made from an aqueous solution containing 22.5 wt% AMPS and 4 wt% MBAA while the light red curves correspond to pAMPS microgels made from a solution encompassing 25 wt% AMPS and 3 wt% MBAA. The composition of these microgels is similar to that used for the pETPTA-DNGHs made from the optimized inks A and B. The Young moduli are (110 ± 10) and (140 ± 10) kPa for pAMPS/pAM DNGHs made of pAMPS microgels similar to those used in ink A and B. The compression moduli are (335 ± 20) and (370 ± 15) kPa, respectively.

Figure S10: Stress-strain curves of bulk pAMPS hydrogels under compression. The light blue curves correspond to pAMPS hydrogels made from an aqueous solution containing 22.5 wt% AMPS and 4 wt% MBAA while the light red curves correspond to pAMPS hydrogels made from a solution encompassing 25 wt% AMPS and 3 wt% MBAA. The compositions of these bulk hydrogels are similar to those used for the pETPTA-DNGHs made from the optimized inks A and B. The compression moduli are (226 ± 16) and (202 ± 3) kPa, respectively.

Figure S11: Mechanical properties of pETPTA-DNGHs composed of (a) pETPTA microparticles and pAMPS microgels at weight fractions of 5 (●), 3.3 (●), 2.5 (●), 2 (●) and 1.7 wt% (●), (b) pAMPS particles produced from precursor solutions containing 2 (●), 3 (●), 4 (●), 5 (●) and 6 wt% (●) MBAA and 25 wt% AMPS and (c) with a 2nd network containing 0.1 (●), 0.5 (●), 0.9 (●), 1.3 (●) and 2 wt% (●) MBAA. The 2 wt% pAMPS microgels are produced from a precursor solution containing 25 wt% AMPS and 3 wt% MBAA. The (i) stress-strain curves are used to calculate the (ii) stress at break of each ink.

Figure S12: Photographs of flawed dogbones composed of a mixture of pETPTA microparticles and stiff pAMPS microgels made from a solution containing 25 wt% AMPS and 5 to 6 wt% MBAA. (a) An inhomogeneous polymerization of the dogbone-shaped samples results in macroscopic defects. (b) An insufficient amount of 2nd network leads to thinner dogbones because pAMPS microgels located towards the surfaces of the samples are not firmly attached to the samples. Scale bars: 5 mm.

Figure S13: Characterization of the photonic granular mixed inks. (a) Amplitude and (b) frequency sweeps performed on the photonic inks used to print the triskele (●), the blue part of the butterfly (●) and the green one (●). SEM images of the surface of a (c) NP-free pETPTA microparticle and (d) photonic pETPTA microparticle made from a precursor solution containing ETPTA:EGPEA (1:1), 13 vol% SiO₂ (130 nm) and PI. Scale bars: 1 μ m.

Figure S14: Observation of the photonic crystal structures at the nanometer and centimeter scales. SEM images of the cross-section of a (a) blue and (b) green photonic pETPTA microparticles. Scales bars: 20 μm . The inset SEM images show the periodic arrangement of the SiO₂ NPs towards the surface of the photonic microparticles, thereby leading to the formation of structural colors. Scale bars: 1 μm . Photographs of the 3D printed butterfly made from a mixture of similar photonic microparticles and pAMPS microgels made from a solution containing 25 wt% AMPS and 3 wt% MBAA, taken (c) in the dry state where incoherent scattering leads to a whitish appearance (scale bars: 2 μm and 500 μm) and (d) in the wet state where the blue structural color can be observed if placed on a dark background. Scale bar: 2 μm . The printed structure is flexible despite of the high stiffness of pETPTA microparticles.

Figure S15: (a) Schematic illustration and photographs of the photonic butterfly illuminated with a white light at different angles, from 0° to 60° . The colors are non-iridescent and remain stable over a wide range of illumination angles. Scale bar: 1 cm. Reflectance measurements taken on the (b) blue and (c) green regions of the butterfly acquired at illumination angles that vary between 0° (light colors) and 60° (dark colors).

Figure S16: Optical micrographs of microfragments used to fabricate the temperature-responsive photonic device. (a) Optical micrograph of pNIPAM fragments obtained by cryomilling bulk pNIPAM made from a solution containing 15 wt% NIPAM and 1 wt% MBAA. Scale bar: 250 μm . (b) Optical micrograph of pETPTA microparticles made from an ETPTA solution containing 33 vol% of SiO_2 NPs. This dispersion is emulsified in water via vortexing. Scale bar: 250 μm . (c) Transmittance spectra of bulk pNIPAM at room temperature (\bullet), when

heated above the LCST (●), and after 1 hr of cooling to room temperature (●) showing a strong decrease of the transmittance in the visible range as the temperature increases.

Figure S17: Optical properties of the temperature sensitive photonic devices. (a) Photographs of blue and green photonic sensors in various shapes, first when heated at 36°C (top) and after 9 min of cooling (bottom). The corresponding reflectance spectra for (b) the blue and (c) green devices are measured every 3 min as the sensors cool down from 36°C. As expected, a significant increase in the reflectance peak intensity is observed as the sensors cool down.